

BREADBOARD TESTING OF THE LUNAR VOLATILES SCOUT FOR THE MAGPIE MISSION.

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Lunar Volatiles Scout: The Lunar Volatiles Scout (LVS) instrument [1] is destined to fly to the Moon as part of ESA's Mission for Advanced Geophysics and Polar Ice Exploration (MAGPIE), led by ispace Europe [2]. The LVS aims to characterise water and other volatiles, and the geophysical properties of lunar regolith at several drilling sites in the polar region. The concept of the LVS builds on the results of previous joint instrument and rover studies led by the Technical University of Munich [1,3–5]. The instrument functions by inserting a hollow drill shell with a central heating element into the soil to thermally extract bound volatiles, which are then analysed with a mass spectrometer. In addition, force and torque are measured during the insertion process to infer geotechnical properties of the lunar subsurface. The advantage of the LVS is that the instrument is brought to the sample, reducing potential losses of volatiles during sample handling.

Figure 1: CAD rendering of the VS section of the LVS instrument on MAGPIE

The LVS consists of five key subsystems: The Volatiles Sampler (VS) is a hollow core drill with a central heating element, equipped with pressure and temperature sensors to monitor the extraction process. The VS can sample to a nominal depth of 100 mm in lunar soil. The Drill Translation Unit (DTU) is used to insert and retract the VS into and from the lunar soil. To analyse the gases evolved during soil heating, the LVS includes an ion-trap mass spectrometer, the Volatiles Analyser (VA). A Gas Transfer Pipe (GTP) connects the VS and VA sections to deliver the evolved gases to the mass spectrometer. All instrument units are controlled by the Control Unit (CU) within the MAGPIE rover electronics.

The LVS is developed as a payload for the MAGPIE mission by a consortium between the Technical University of Munich, The Open University (responsible for the VA), ESR Technology (responsible for the DTU), and ispace Europe (responsible for the CU).

Test Objectives: Since the LVS was reconfigured to meet the MAGPIE rover's accommodation requirements, the breadboard tests aim to verify the functionality of this new design. This includes drilling into ice-bearing regolith simulants in a temperature-controlled vacuum chamber, thermal extraction of water from the sample, and live analysis of water and other released volatiles using a mass spectrometer. Furthermore, the breadboard test campaign aims to test and verify the newly added GTP interface and the VS thermal model. It is expected that earlier results on drilling and gas extraction with the heritage design [3–5] can be replicated, to de-risk and gain confidence in the design for the next phase of the mission.

Breadboard Tests: The test setup is illustrated in Figure 2. Inside the temperature-controlled vacuum chamber, the VS is fully assembled and attached to a linear stage emulating the DTU. The prototype GTP is connected to a feedthrough exiting the main chamber, which in turn connects to a smaller secondary chamber where a mass spectrometer is operated. For the purpose of this test campaign, a commercial quadrupole mass spectrometer is used. The sample temperature is monitored at four locations, and the VS and GTP temperatures are monitored at six locations.

A pre-conditioned sample of a lunar regolith simulant, containing approximately 5 % water ice by mass, is positioned in the sample cooling shroud. Liquid nitrogen is cycled in the cooling shroud to cool the sample during the pumping and test phases. Pressures below $1e-5$ mbar are intended to be reached for the main and secondary chamber. In addition, the GTP is

heated to approximately 75 °C (TBC) to prevent volatile adsorption onto the interior pipe walls.

The VS functional operation is flight representative, comprising a full cycle of lowering via a linear stage, drilling, heating, and retraction. During heating, the heater consumes up to 15 W for up to 90 min, while according to predictions, the sample reaches temperatures of more than 400 K, sufficient to desorb most water ice from the sample. Two pressure sensors integrated into the VS will monitor pressure in the sample compartment and along the gas transfer path. Since both are separated by an orifice, the mass transfer of volatiles can be deduced from the pressure readings.

Figure 2: Setup for the breadboard test campaign of the LVS

Outlook: The completion of breadboard testing represents a significant milestone for the LVS development within the MAGPIE mission. The operation of the reconfigured VS design will be verified independently of other subsystems. The breadboard test results will inform both the design and testing of the Demonstration Model planned for later in 2026. Unlike the breadboard presented here, the Demonstration Model will include representative models of the VA, DTU, and GTP and will serve as the baseline for the final configuration of the Lunar Volatiles Scout.

References: [1] Gscheidle C. et al. (2022) *PSS*, 212, 105426. [2] Casanova S. et al. (2026) *this conference* [3] Biswas J. et al. (2020) *PSS*, 181, 104826. [4] Biswas et al. (2019), *ELS*. [5] Biswas et al. (2018), *ELS*.